

Menstrual Health Management among Medical Students as a Consequence of Menstrual Health Policies in India- A Cross Sectional StudyShashikala N¹, Bhagyashree Kathari²¹Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Subbaiah Institute of Medical Sciences, Shivamogga²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Subbaiah Institute of Medical Sciences, Shivamogga

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Healthy menstrual hygiene management (MHM) includes the usage of safe materials, access to privacy, cleaning private parts with soap and water and safe disposal of the menstrual material. However, insufficient/ inaccurate knowledge, lack of support and resources are some challenges responsible for knowledge and practice gaps seen in relation to menstruation among adolescents. The cultural, psychosocial, environmental and economic aspects of menstruations are inadequately addressed by the MHM programmes in India.

Objectives: To assess the knowledge and practices related to menstruation on attaining menarche, menstrual health and its environmental impact and to determine the hygienic practices and experiences during menstruation among female medical students.

Materials and methods: Cross section study among female students using self-administered questionnaire was conducted in a medical college in Karnataka.

Results: The average age of the students was 20.46 ± 1.35 years and age of menarche was 13.25 ± 1.302 years. Majority of them (93.1%) received information about menstruation before menarche, mainly from their mothers (61%), used sanitary pads (90.1%), nearly 61.4% had satisfactory hygienic practices, and however disposal of the menstrual products, knowledge related to environmental and economic impact was poor among 80% of the students. Most of the students 75.5% followed some social and cultural restrictions during menarche and 42.8% missed college during their last menstrual cycle.

Conclusion: Gaps in knowledge related to menstrual health, dysmenorrhoea, waste disposal, hygienic practices, psychosocial aspects, environmental impact and reusable products emphasis attention through MHM programme ensuring social integration and reduce discrimination or stigmatization.

Keywords: Dysmenorrhoea, Medical students, MHM, Menstrual waste disposal, menstrual stigma, sanitary pads.

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Introduction

On any given day, more than 800 million women between the ages of 15 and 49 are menstruating around the world. [1] Healthy menstrual hygiene management (MHM) includes the usage of safe materials to adsorb or collect menstrual blood that can be changed as frequently as required and in privacy, cleaning private parts with soap and water, and enabling access to facilities for the safe disposal of the materials used for menstrual management. [2-3] MHM addresses all the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly "universal access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all, and health outcomes related to sexual and reproductive health, as well as addressing the effects of stigma, psychosocial aspects related to menstruation. [4] Use of disposable sanitary pads has become synonymous

with menstrual hygiene as result of rapid urbanization, improved incomes, expanded product availability and distribution, increased mobility and menstrual health policies all over the world. These disposable sanitary pads are however posing a threat to environment and humans as they are improperly disposed and take > 500 year to decompose and the sanitary pads in India have higher content of harmful substances. [5,6,7] The cultural, psychosocial and economic implications of menstruations are inadequately addressed by the MHM programmes in India. However, insufficient/ inaccurate knowledge, lack of support and resources are some major challenges responsible for knowledge gaps seen in relation to menstruation among adolescents. [8]

This study aims to explore the knowledge, practices, and experiences related to menstrual hygiene among undergraduate female medical students. It tries to assess their understanding of menstruation upon reaching menarche, their awareness of menstrual health, and the environmental impact of menstrual products. Additionally, the study will examine their menstrual hygiene practices and personal experiences during menstruation.

Materials & Methods

A cross-sectional study was carried out among female medical undergraduates in a medical college of Karnataka. Using a convenient sampling technique, a survey was conducted with a sample size of 320, calculated based on an estimated 3% prevalence of menstrual cup usage, an allowable error of 2%, and a 10% non-response rate.⁹ After obtaining permission from college authorities and approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee, students were approached post-class hours. Data was collected through a pre-designed, pre-tested, structured, and self-administered anonymous questionnaire distributed via Google Forms. The purpose of the study was explained to the students present on the day of data collection, and only those who provided consent were included. The questionnaire covered various topics, including socio-demographic details, age at menarche, experiences related to the first menstrual cycle, menstrual symptoms, health-seeking behavior, menstrual hygiene practices, menstrual products, and awareness of the environmental and economic impacts of these products. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality was ensured.

Definitions

1. Menstrual Health is a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, in relation to the menstrual cycle as defined by WHO. [10]
2. Menstrual hygiene management (MHM)- Women and adolescent girls are using a clean menstrual management material to absorb or collect menstrual blood, that can be changed in privacy as often as necessary for the duration of a menstrual period, using soap and water for washing the body as required, and having access to safe and convenient facilities to dispose of used menstrual management materials. [2]
3. Menstrual health and hygiene (MHH) - encompasses both MHM and the broader systemic factors that link menstruation with health, well-being, gender equality, education, equity, empowerment, and rights. These systematic factors have been summarized by

UNESCO as accurate and timely knowledge, available, safe, and affordable materials, informed and comfortable professionals, referral and access to health services, sanitation and washing facilities, positive social norms, safe and hygienic disposal and advocacy and policy. [2]

4. Menstrual hygiene materials: are the products used to catch menstrual flow, such as pads, cloths, tampons or cups. [2]
5. Menstrual hygiene practices: washing of genitals > 2 times per day during menstrual cycle is considered satisfactory.
6. Menstrual stigma: refers to the negative perception of menstruation and those who menstruate, characterizing the menstruating body as abnormal and object. [12]

Statistical analysis: The collected data were compiled in Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while quantitative variables were expressed as mean and standard deviation. The chi-square test was employed to determine statistical significance, with a p-value of <0.05 considered significant.

Results

Socio-demographic details: This study presents important insights into menstrual hygiene practices and attitudes among medical students. 290 (91.48%) students among 317 female students responded to the survey. Among the surveyed students 242 (83.4%) are residing in the hostel, 199 (68.6%) come from urban areas, 217 (75%) of fathers and 179 (61%) of mothers are graduates.

The average age of the students was 20.46 ± 1.35 years and age of menarche was 13.25 ± 1.302 years.

First menstrual cycle experience: 270 (93.1%) received education about menstruation before attending menarche. Most of them received the information from their mother 178(61.4%) and also shared their first menstrual cycle experience with their mothers 242(83.4%) and in secondary schools 140 (48.3%). Majority of the female used sanitary pads during their first menstrual cycle 272 (93.8%). However, 216 (74.5%) of the girls followed some socio-cultural restrictions at their homes.

Table 1: Nearly 80% of the students' experienced premenstrual and menstrual symptoms of which dysmenorrhea were seen in 33% of the students, 42.8% missed college. However 275 (94.8%) wanted seek help for the same.

Table 2: Hygienic practices were found to be more satisfactory among medical students from rural backgrounds (69% vs 57.7%, $p=0.063$), those fathers had lower levels of education (75% vs

56.7%, $p=0.005$), and those from middle-income groups (70.6% vs 52% vs 62%, $p=0.031$). Students with menorrhagia (80%, $p=0.016$) and those who changed their sanitary pads more than three times a day (64.5% vs 50%, $p=0.038$) also showed better hygiene practices. Additionally, students who rarely or only sometimes used soap to wash their genitals had more satisfactory hygiene practices (64% vs 46%, $p=0.043$). These differences were statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) between students with satisfactory and unsatisfactory menstrual hygiene practices.

Table 3: First-year students demonstrated better knowledge regarding the decomposition of sanitary pads (54.6%) and the annual menstrual waste generated by women (47.5%) compared to students in the later stages of their course (31.6% and 39.4%, respectively). The duration of menstrual

cup usage and the average money spent on menstrual health were similar across all students. A total of 275 students (94.8%) indicated they would seek help for menstrual problems, yet 124 students (42.8%) reported missing college during their cycle due to menstrual issues.

Reusable menstrual product users: The majority of students using reusable menstrual materials (18, 81.8%) were from urban areas, with 18 (81.8%) using reusable sanitary pads. Among them, 8 (36.3%) were first-year students, and 90-100% of their parents were graduates or had higher education. Despite this, their hygiene practices were similar to those of other students. However, their knowledge and practices related to menstrual cup usage were inadequate—they boiled the menstrual cup more than once during the cycle and boiled it for more than 10 minutes.

Table 1: Distribution of premenstrual and menstrual symptoms among the study participants.

Sl No	Variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Menstrual symptoms		
	Low back pain	238	82.1
	Nausea	46	15.9
	Vomiting	25	8.6
	Giddiness	50	17.2
	Dysmenorrhea	96	33.1
	Menorrhagia	35	12.1
2.	Premenstrual symptoms	243	83.8
	Mood swings	179	61.7
	Tiredness	71	24.5
	Headache	63	21.7
	Insomnia	27	9.3
	Acne	154	53.1
	Tenderness in breast	78	26.9
	Constipation	20	6.9
	Loose stools	44	15.2
	Low back pain	170	58.6
3.	Not attending to work/college in the last Menstrual cycle.	124	42.8
4.	Want to seek help from doctor for menstrual problems.	275	94.8

Table 2: Menstrual hygiene practices among female medical students and their association with socio-demographic profile, knowledge and practices related to menstrual health.

Sl no	Variable	Not satisfactory hygiene practices (112)	Satisfactory hygiene practices (178)	Total (290)	P value
1	Place of residence				.063
	Urban	84 (75.0%)	115 (64.6%)	199 (68.6%)	
	Rural	28 (25.0%)	63 (35.4%)	91 (31.4%)	
2	Father education				0.005
	Non-graduate	18 (16.1%)	55 (30.9%)	73 (25.2%)	
	Graduate and above	94 (83.9%)	123 (69.1%)	217 (74.8%)	
3	Mother education				0.145
	Non-graduate	37(33.0%)	74 (41.6%)	111(38.3%)	
	Graduate and above	75 (67.0%)	104 (58.4%)	179 (61.7%)	
4	Socio economic class				

	Middle	27 (24.1%)	65(36.5%)	92(31.7%)	0.031
	Upper middle	47(42.0%)	51(28.7%)	98(33.8%)	
	Upper	38 (33.9%)	62 (34.8%)	100 (34.5%)	
5	Year of study				
	I st Year	37 (33.0%)	60(33.7%)	97 (33.4%)	0.547
	II nd Year and above	75(67.0%)	118 (66.3%)	193 (66.6%)	
6	Menorrhagia				
	Absent	105 (93.8%)	150 (84.3%)	255(87.9%)	0.016
	Present	7 (6.2%)	28(15.7%)	35(12.1%)	
7	Health care seeking behavior for menstrual problems.				
	No	4(3.6%)	11(6.2%)	15(5.2%)	0.329
	Yes	108 (96.4%)	167(93.8%)	275 (94.8%)	
8	Menstrual products used				
	Single use disposable products(sanitary pads and tampons)	102 (91.1%)	166 (93.3%)	268(92.4%)	0.493
	Reusable products	10 (8.9%)	12 (6.7%)	22 (7.6%)	
9	Hand washing before changing menstrual material				
	Never	6(5.4%)	18(10.1%)	24(8.3%)	0.178
	Sometimes	44 (39.3%)	55(30.9%)	99 (34.1%)	
	Always	62 (55.4%)	105(59.0%)	167(57.6%)	
10	Hand washing after changing menstrual material				
	Sometimes	1(0.9%)	6(3.4%)	7 (2.4%)	0.181
	Always	111(99.1%)	172 (96.6%)	283(97.6%)	
11	Whether soap was used for hand washing				
	Never	33(29.5%)	55(30.9%)	88(30.3%)	0.043
	Sometimes	52(46.4%)	100(56.2%)	152(52.4%)	
	Always	27(24.1%)	23(12.9%)	50(17.2%)	
12	Material used for wrapping the menstrual waste before disposing it.				
	Plastic cover of the pad	69(61.6%)	102(57.3%)	171(58.9%)	0.870
	In Paper	29(25.9%)	52(29.2%)	81(27.9%)	
	In Cloth	14(12.5%)	24(13.5%)	38(13.1%)	
13	Number of times the menstrual product changed on the heaviest day of menstruation				
	< 2 times	31(27.7%)	31(17.4%)	62(21.4%)	0.038
	> 3times	81(72.3%)	147(82.6%)	228(78.6%)	

Table 3: Knowledge regarding menstrual products and health seeking behavior among medical students according to number of years in college

Sl no	Variables	1 st year	2 nd year and above	Total	P value
1	Time taken for decomposition of sanitary pads				0.002
	5-10 yrs	28(28.9%)	79(40.9%)	107(36.9%)	
	1-2 yrs	16 (16.5%)	53(27.5%)	69(23.8%)	
	> 500 yrs	29(29.9%)	37(19.2%)	66(22.8%)	
2	Sanitary waste generated by women per year.				0.045
	150 Kgs	15(15.5%)	40(20.7%)	55(19.0%)	
	60 Kgs	27(27.8%)	53(27.5%)	80(27.6%)	
	40 Kgs	24(24.7%)	65(33.7%)	89(30.7%)	
3	Mean usage time for Silicone menstrual cup				0.152
	6 months	47(48.5%)	84(43.5%)	131(45.2%)	
	Single use	12(12.4%)	14(7.3%)	26(9.0%)	
	2-3 yrs	24(24.7%)	71(36.8%)	95(32.8%)	
4	Money spent on menstrual products per month				0.058
	< 100	9(9.3%)	31(16.1%)	40(13.8%)	
	100-300	35(36.1%)	70(36.3%)	105(36.2%)	
	300-500	25(25.8%)	60(31.1%)	85(29.3%)	

	>500	28(28.9%)	32(16.6%)	60(20.7%)	
5	Want to seek help from doctor for menstrual problems.				
	Yes	91(93.8%)	184(95.3%)	275(94.8%)	0.581
6	Not attending to work/college in the last menstrual cycle.				
	No	57(58.8%)	109(56.5%)	166(57.2%)	0.710
	Yes	40(41.2%)	84(43.5%)	124(42.8%)	

Graph 1: Distribution of female medical students based on the source of information received on menstruation

Graph 2: Distribution of female medical students based on social and cultural restrictions followed during first menstrual cycle

Graph 3: Characteristics of the medical students using reusable menstrual products (n=22)

Graph 4: Practices related to menstrual cup usage among the female medical students (n=6)

Discussion

Half of the global population, women menstruate as a natural process for 7-8 years in their life time. Despite its universality, menstruation is often surrounded by secrecy and silence, burdened by socio cultural misconceptions and taboos making it a difficult topic to be discuss, thus leaving a larger aspect of MHM not addressed adequately. The present study highlights, pursuing higher education does not ensure hygienic menstrual practices, and hence addressing menstrual health is essential at all stages of reproductive life. The mean age of menarche in our study was 13.25±1.3 years, closely aligning with findings from various other studies conducted across different populations in India. [13-15] In our study, nearly 93% of participants

were aware of menstruation before experiencing menarche, consistent with the study by Jabeen et al. [12] However, our participants demonstrated a higher level of pre-menorrhoeal knowledge, compared to medical students surveyed from other regions in the country, where awareness ranged from 56.92% to 84.24%. [13,14-15]

This suggests an improved awareness among girls about menstruation, as an impact of MHM program. [8] Mothers role in imparting MHM is vital as nearly 93 % of the students had knowledge about menstruation before attending menarche, among whom 61 % received information through their mothers and also shared their first menstrual cycle experience 242(83.4%) with them. Secondary schools 140 (48.3%) and peers (24%) significantly

contributed to their knowledge about MHM. However, similarly studies also reported mother as their first source of information by 82.4% and 84.8% respectively. [18,19] These findings are similar to various studies done across the world however, inadequate and untimely education around menstruation perpetuates confusion and anxiety among the adolescents. [8]

Majority of the female used sanitary pads during their first menstrual cycle 272 (93.8%) and 290 (90.3%) continue to use it, although 8% opting for reusable menstrual products like menstrual cups, period underwear, and reusable sanitary pads, consistent with findings from other studies across India [13-17] A study by Kumar B et al has found hazardous chemicals like dioxin, toluene, furans, isopropyl alcohol in Indian sanitary pad at higher concentrations compared to its counterparts in developed countries. [7,20] Though there is potential to promote reusable alternatives like menstrual cups, period underwear's and reusable sanitary pads, alternate menstrual hygiene options beyond sanitary pads are infrequently discussed. [21]

Nearly, 216 (74.5%) of the girls followed some socio-cultural restrictions at their homes. The socio-cultural practices are seen in all cultures around the world, signifying the fact that menstruation has been considered as an important event in a women's life. However, social segregation and behavioral restrictions during menstruation reflects the persisting stigma of menstruation as an impurity. Most of the MHM programmes are directed towards raising awareness among adolescent girls, increase access to and use of sanitary pads, and ensure safe disposal of pads, solely focusing on practical and physical aspects of menstruation management while excluding psychosocial conditions that create the stigmatized environment of menstruation. [22]

A total of 42.8% (124) reported avoiding college during menstruation, while 94.8% (275) expressed a willingness to seek help from healthcare providers for menstrual issues in our study. An review by Maity et al revealed that menstrual disturbances, including dysmenorrhea, PMS, and PMDD, significantly impair academic performance and well-being in female medical students as result of absenteeism, lack of concentration, and anxiety. [23] Menstrual health issues remain under-addressed beyond high school and sanitary pads, thus its inclusion at all life stages of women's will promote gender equality in academic and working environments. The government polices across the countries are supporting menstrual leave policies in educational institutions and workplaces to address painful menstruation, however this may be critical to women empowerment creating barriers for women's productivity and inclusion in society. In

the present study, commonly reported premenstrual and menstrual symptoms were mood swings (61.7%), low back pain (58.6%), and acne (53.1%) and 82% experiencing low back pain, 33% dysmenorrhea (painful periods) respectively similar to other studies. [14,15] Although nearly 42% missed college due to menstrual discomfort respectively similar to other studies. Lifestyle changes like poor nutrition and unhealthy eating habits, inadequate or irregular sleep Higher stress levels, often due to academic, social, or work-related pressures, have been found to exacerbate menstrual pain leading to the rising prevalence of dysmenorrhea (painful periods) in recent years, particularly among adolescent girls and young women, affecting the overall well-being and daily functioning of young women and girls. [24-27] Incorporating MHM education into the higher educational institutions as well can be crucial in addressing dysmenorrhea and fostering a healthier, more informed approach to menstrual health.

Menstrual hygiene practices, particularly hand washing and genital washing, were found to be inadequate among many participants in our study. Only 57.6% of participants washed their hands before changing menstrual pads, and of these, 82.7% either rarely or never used soap, however, hand washing after changing pads was more common, with 97.6% of participants practicing it. About 15.8% of participants washed their genitals less than twice per day during menstruation. Most of the studies across India showed inconsistencies in menstrual hygiene practices, thus highlight the need for Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) sensitization programs. [13,14,16,17]

These programs should emphasize proper hand and genital hygiene during menstruation and ensure access to essential resources like soap, water, and adequate privacy to enable hygienic practices. Higher levels of parental education was associated with good menstrual hygiene practices, increasing with higher educational attainment AOR = 1.96, and 3.54 for secondary education and graduation and above in mothers and AOR = 2.31, and 2.86 for secondary education and graduate and above in fathers. [18] our study showed association between menstrual hygiene practices with paternal education and socioeconomic class($p < 0.05$).

Menstrual product disposal practices contribute to environmental pollution, as highlighted by our study in which 58.6% of participants wrapped sanitary pads in plastic and 92.4% disposed of them with household waste. The MHM report also reported 70% of urban and 51% of slum dwellers disposed the menstrual waste with house hold waste, and 28-30% of rural and slum dwellers disposed it in the open. [28] Menstrual waste disposal though addressed in the MHM programme, its final destination of the sanitary pad is not deliberated

upon. [29] Menstrual waste disposal needs to be regulated by encouraging wrapping pads in biodegradable materials, like paper, establishing separate disposal systems and building incinerators in hostels and other establishments where large groups of reproductive-age women reside. [17,30-32] Additionally, promotion and advocacy for menstrual cups should be prioritized as a sustainable alternative to disposable sanitary pads as they are environmentally friendly and aligning with global efforts toward environmental sustainability. [29]

The critical gap in knowledge about sustainable menstrual practices, environmental and economic benefits of switching to reusable menstrual products and spending nearly Rs 3,600/- to Rs 6,000/- annually on disposable menstrual products. According to UNICEF lack of supportive systems for waste disposal, awareness and research funding are some of the barriers encountered along with social stigma in addressing the above factors despite public acknowledgement of inadequate sanitary waste management. [33]

Conclusion

The awareness about menstruation before menarche, use of sanitary pads is relatively good among the adolescent girls, however, significant knowledge gaps remain, particularly regarding menstrual hygiene, alternatives like reusable products, menstrual waste disposal and environmental impacts of single-use products. Menstrual health policies should address the evolving issues like dysmenorrhea, persisting psychosocial factors that negatively affect women's comfort and social integration and to carefully craft the menstrual leave policy to avoid further exacerbation of workplace discrimination or stigmatization. Menstrual waste disposal, often neglected aspect of menstrual hygiene management (MHM) requires greater attention. Emphasizing proper disposal practices, harmful health and environmental impact is essential to ensure that individuals can make informed, sustainable choices that protect the environment and minimize adverse effects on human health. Sustainable disposal methods should be promoted to reduce environmental impact and support long-term public health.

Recommendations

Comprehensive menstrual hygiene management (MHM) programs in higher educational institutions should expand menstrual health education to cover psychosocial well-being, emerging menstrual issues such as dysmenorrhea, as well as environmental and economic concerns. By encouraging a gradual shift towards sustainable MHM, these institutions can foster an inclusive and supportive environment that promotes menstrual health with safety and dignity. Such programs will not only empower

women and girls, but also addressing broader societal and environmental challenges. As a result, women can reduce their ecological footprint, achieve financial savings, and improve health outcomes through safer, more hygienic practices.

Ethical Clearance: Taken from the Institutional Ethical Committee of Subbaiah Institute of Medical Sciences, Shivamogga, Karnataka.

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